

Prehistoric hunting megastructures in the Adriatic hinterland

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Abstract

Large-scale linear stone alignments, commonly referred to as ‘desert kites’, are well-documented across the arid landscapes of North Africa, the Near East, and Central Asia, where they were used for communal hunting of ungulates. Until now, no comparable structures have been identified in Europe. Here, we report the discovery of four extensive prehistoric structures in the Karst Plateau of the Adriatic hinterland, revealed through airborne laser scanning (ALS). These features consist of low dry-stone walls that converge into deep enclosures strategically positioned beneath natural drops. Their placement on natural movement corridors suggests they functioned as large-scale traps designed to capture herds of wild animals, representing the first evidence of such hunting megastructures in Europe. Excavations and radiocarbon dating indicate that the structures were abandoned before the Late Bronze Age, suggesting an origin potentially in the Mesolithic or earlier. The architectural complexity and estimated construction effort, requiring significant coordination and labour, underscore their importance within past subsistence strategies. GIS-based analyses further demonstrate that these structures were deliberately positioned within the topography to maximize their effectiveness in channelling animal movement. Given the regional distribution of Mesolithic sites, these megastructures may have been used for mass hunting of deer, a key prey species in the area. Our findings challenge existing paradigms of prehistoric hunting strategies in Europe and highlight the previously unrecognized role of large-scale communal hunting in the prehistoric Adriatic landscape.

Introduction

In the arid parts of the Old World, stretching from North Africa ¹, Sinai and southern Negev ^{2,3}, Jordan and Syria ⁴⁻⁶, Arabian Peninsula ^{4,7}, Southeast Anatolia ⁸, Armenia ⁹, and Aralo-Caspian region ^{10,11}, one can find large linear stone alignments, known as ‘desert kites’ due to their distinct shape and large size that is easily identified on aerial and satellite photographs. These structures can extend over several hundred meters to several kilometres. Ethnographic ^{4,6} and archaeological research ^{12,13} have led to a general consensus that the majority of those structures have been used for communal hunting of ungulates, such as

gazelles. However, some of these structures have also been interpreted as an infrastructure for managing and corralling herds of domestic animals ^{9,14,15}.

European prehistory generally lacks such structures, although systems of pitfalls or trapping pits used for elk or reindeer hunting can be found in Scandinavia ¹⁶; and there was recently discovered a submerged wall in the Baltic that could be part of a late glacial structure built to channel movements of migratory reindeer ¹⁷.

Our research, based on an airborne laser scanning (ALS) imagery survey of the Karts plateau in the hinterland of the Gulf of Trieste, on the border between Slovenia and Italy, has revealed four huge structures arranged over a distance of over 25 km (Fig. 1), located on the passes over the central chain of hills. These structures share a common design: low dry-stone walls or stone alignments that converge into a deep enclosure, almost always located beneath a natural drop, a rock ledge at the edge of a doline. The length of stone walls ranges from several hundred meters to several kilometres.

Their shape and deliberate placement on natural corridors and passes suggest their function was in controlling and channelling movement, which, in turn, suggests that these are landscape structures built for trapping herds of wild animals (Fig. 2). We present the first evidence of such structures in Europe, especially structures that are directly comparable to similar structures in North Africa, the Near East, the Caucasus, and the Aralo-Caspian lowlands.

Fig. 1: The Karst and the location of the structures.

Fig. 2: The plans of structures.

Context

The Karst (Kras in Slovenian, Carso in Italian) is a 40 km long and up to 13 km wide limestone plateau above the Gulf of Trieste, the northernmost part of the Adriatic Sea. The terrain is a relatively level surface inclined northwest, featuring numerous dolines, caves, and other karstic phenomena. Elevations range from below 50 m in the northwest to about 500 m in the southeast. Although not exceptionally high, it is a well-defined plateau with visually

striking steep limestone slopes rising from the sea and neighbouring lowlands. At the same time, transitions to the eastern regions of Čičarija and Podgorski Kras are more gradual. There is a belt of slightly higher relief in the central part of the plateau, a chain of hills called Volnik and Tabor Hills, dissected by large depressions. The Karst lacks surface streams as rainwater immediately infiltrates the porous carbonate rock ¹⁸.

Karst has a sub-Mediterranean climate, characterised by warm, dry summers and precipitation peaks in autumn and spring. Winters are cold, with strong continental influences, particularly from the NE wind bora (burja). Historically, the plateau was largely barren due to extensive pasturing, but in recent decades, shrubs and trees have reclaimed much of the landscape.

Palaeoenvironmental studies suggest that during the Late Glacial period, the Karst was covered by scanty open pine-birch forests, with oak and other deciduous species appearing around the transition to the Holocene ¹⁹. From approximately 9000 to 4000 BP, oak-hornbeam forests became dominant. Human influence on vegetation became evident in the mid-Holocene, leading to the growth of heliophyte shrubs such as cornelian cherry, blackthorn, and hazel ²⁰⁻²².

Archaeological research of Karst began in the late 19th century, uncovering remains of over 100 prehistoric sites. Late Palaeolithic evidence is very sparse, but there is significant Mesolithic presence, making this area a south-eastern edge of a dense concentration of Mesolithic sites in the south-eastern Alps and Veneto-Friulan plain, one of the richest Mesolithic areas in Europe ^{23,24}. During the Neolithic, caves were used as herding camps for nomadic pastoralists, who moved with their specialised herds of sheep and goats ^{25,26}. However, extensive landscape modifications occurred from around 4500 BP, particularly between 4000 and 3000 BP. This period saw significant deforestation through burning, evidenced by doline infills containing charcoal and burnt soil. These changes marked the

emergence of a cultural landscape featuring permanent stone structures, including monumental hillforts, barrows, cairns, and stone walls. These developments reflect a transition to more settled pastoral communities. Moreover, there is also a layer of early modern reorganisation of the landscape, which formed the modern cultural landscape ²⁷.

Results of airborne laser scanning survey

Natural processes on the Karst plateau are slow, with erosion primarily removing fine sediments that accumulate in depressions, dolines, and caves. As a result, anthropogenic movement and rearrangement of local limestone leave lasting positive topographic anomalies, such as banks, cairns, and walls. The Karst landscape is, therefore, an archive of past human interventions. Using airborne laser scanning, we mapped and identified numerous features, including cairnfields, enclosures, driveways, and field boundaries, that make up the prehistoric cultural landscape formed around Bronze Age hillforts.

However, the survey also detected four unusual structures that do not easily fit into the pattern of the Bronze Age cultural landscape. These features consist of faint, elongated linear stone alignments or low walls that form a distinct funnel shape, converging at a small sub-rectangular enclosure, typically around 8 to 10 m in size. The enclosures are deep structures, often built within doline and placed below natural vertical drops, escarpments, or crags.

Two of these structures (K01 and K02), located in the eastern part of the Karst plateau, are more complex, incorporating two additional lateral funnels and enclosures into their design (Fig. 2).

The structures appear as linear stone piles or unstructured walls composed of relatively large, local, heavy-weathered limestone stones (Fig. 3). The limestone blocks are readily available in the landscape. Large stones are loosely stacked in two parallel rows or faces and packed with smaller stones and rubble, resulting in an irregular dry-stone wall.

Sometimes, very large blocks or stones (>1 m) are incorporated into the structure. These stones are sometimes existing rough limestone outcrops, pitted and featuring dissolution channels. Based on the orientation of dissolution channels, it seems that some of the massive blocks were moved or rotated in place. In some cases, walls follow the orientation of limestone pavements, incorporating clints into the design.

Their width varies between 1 and 1.5 m. Their height, in some cases preserved up to 2 or 3 courses high, rarely exceeds 0.5 meters. The paucity of collapsed material nearby suggests that the walls were never significantly taller. In some sections, especially closer to the funnel's convergence point, the walls become lower and less carefully built. The result is a low line of stones that is more a visual marker in a landscape than an actual obstacle.

Fig. 3: Driving walls as recorded on the field.

Fig. 4: Funnels of the K01 structure on ALS imagery.

The walls are relatively long, with the total length of walls reaching 3.5 km in the K01 and 530 m with the smallest structure, K03.

Despite their overall completeness, some gaps are present. These gaps are rarely due to later destruction; instead, they often align with natural stony crags or steep doline edges, integrating the terrain's natural features into their design.

In certain instances, the materials from the walls were repurposed during the early modern period to construct dry-stone boundaries. These sections of walls have been raised with early modern and integrated into contemporary field divisions, functioning as traditional boundary dry-stone walls or serving as stone cairns for clearance purposes.

Walls are skillfully integrated into a landscape, following and enhancing the utilising of the natural lines in a landscape, such as ridges and built around significant forms, such as basins and saddles. They are constructed on slopes, facing downslope, with the apex typically situated at the lowest point of the structure. The relative height of the structure can reach up to 75 meters (as seen in K01), reflecting the rugged and varied landscape topography in which they are incorporated.

At the apex of the walls, sub-rectangular enclosures or cells are constructed. These serve as both continuations and terminations of the walls, but they are erected beneath the crag or cliff, typically situated within a doline. They take advantage of the lower ground, thereby enhancing the height difference. These hollow structures have sides measuring between 8 and 10 meters in length, with a cliff or crag forming one side, enclosing a subrectangular area of approximately 25 square meters (Fig. 5).

Similar to walls, they are constructed of locally corroded blocks of limestone. However, the enclosures are much more massive and carefully built than the walls. Excavation of cell in structure K01 revealed that the wall was built directly on compact limestone bedstone dissected by dissolution channels and grikes, and filled with terra-rosa, reddish, clayey to silty soil with neutral pH conditions that resulted from limestone weathering. The width of the walls at the base is estimated to be around 2.5 m; the base of the walls is built of relatively large blocks up to 0.7 m in size, weighing a few hundred kg. They are stacked at least four to five courses high, with smaller stones on top and packing the voids between large stones. The walls are still preserved to around 1.5 m in height; based on the volume of rubble, we estimate that the wall was about 2-2.5 m high originally.

Fig. 5: The pit trap at the apex of the K01 structure.

The walls lean on the crag or cliff; the top of the crag break can rise up to 3.5 – 4 m above the lowest point in the enclosure, creating a significant vertical drop.

Dating

Post-depositional processes filled the enclosure with the rubble of the collapsed enclosure wall and humus soil (Fig. 6). Below the rubble layer, we identified a thin (0.1 - 0.2 m) layer of silty clay with a darker reddish-brown colour, interpreted as a buried ground that

formed within the enclosure after abandonment. Three fragments of oak charcoal and a flint bladelet were recovered from this layer, and several small orange lumps of burnt clay and silt were found. The bladelet is made from heavily corroded local low-quality flint.

Fig 6. The section through the pit in the apex of K01 and the position of test trench in the pit.

Radiocarbon dating of three charcoal fragments dates the buried ground to the period between the Late Bronze Age (3500 BP) and the Roman era (1700 BP). Since the samples are derived from the buried ground within the structure, they indicate a later phase of the structure's use or, more likely, a period when the surrounding landscape was utilised for different activities. Indeed, these dates align closely with the timeline of human impact identified in over 20 dolines in the area. This impact is evidenced by the presence of

charcoal, lumps of burned clay, pottery fragments, and increased magnetic susceptibility, all of which suggest an episode of burning and forest clearance occurring between 4000 and 2000 BP. This period is also associated with higher sedimentation rates^{27,28}.

Thus, the dates establish a *terminus ante quem for the structure*; by the time the surrounding forest was cleared during the Bronze Age, the structure was already in place and was likely abandoned.

Topographical positioning

The structures are strategically placed within the terrain, leveraging the complex topography to channel movement. They effectively utilise valleys, ridges, and slopes to channel movement towards the structures. For instance, the complex structures K01 and K02 are located near the Sežana Gate, a natural corridor that links the central plateau (Komen and Sežana Karst) with the Trieste Karst above the Gulf of Trieste. Rather than obstructing the corridor itself, the structures are situated laterally, allowing them to control movement across the low hills that border the corridor, potentially using basins and valleys to gather and concentrate animals. The complexity of the terrain is further demonstrated by the construction of lateral funnels in those constructions.

Fig. 7: Position of a K01 structure in a landscape, view from the southeast. Apex is at the bottom.

The K01, the largest structure, has guiding walls that follow ridge crests and high ground, guiding animals toward the saddle between two hilltops . The saddle acts as a natural gateway to channel movement over the crest, where the driving walls lead downslope toward a shallow basin at the foot of the hill. The route ends with two connected large dolines, with an enclosure concealed in the last one.

Additionally, the structure incorporates two small lateral funnels strategically positioned to manage any lateral movement that might seek to return across the crest. These funnels effectively direct animals toward enclosures hidden behind the low crests.

K02 is positioned to control movement on both sides of a low hill. Laterally positioned funnels and enclosures also control lateral movement, with the apex of the main funnel in a small doline at the bottom of the hill.

K03 and K04 feature a more straightforward position, as both are designed to manage movement through a valley. The smaller K03 is located on the slope of a minor valley that offers a passage over the central hills, connecting Nabrežina plain to the Komen Karst of the central plateau. In contrast, the K04 obstructs one of the primary natural corridors in the Karst, effectively blocking a dry valley that extends from the Komen Karst of the central plateau toward the west, leading into the Friuli Plain.

Visibility analysis indicates that the guiding walls direct movement to slopes with a good overview and a well-controlled landscape (Fig. 7). The walls are positioned so that they are visible from within the structure, defining a visible envelope. Once positioned within the structure, they would be visible and would lead downwards to a more sheltered location, subtly guiding movement towards the apex.

The pits are skillfully concealed and only become visible during the final stages of the approach. They are not only hidden below the cliff or crag in a doline, utilising lower terrain for concealment, but also positioned just over a low ridge or summit, which blocks the view toward the apex when approaching. The gentle incline of the approach, combined with the plateau and ridge summit, conceals the cliff and pit until the final meters when one crosses the top. Here, the driving walls narrow and form a narrow, 3-4 meters wide corridor, ending in an enclosure below the cliff.

Fig. 7: Visibility analysis of pit traps, the guiding walls and the visual structure of the landscape around the structure K01. The terrain profile approaching the apex of K01.

Architectural energetics

Those large structures were not endeavours that small groups could feasibly undertake due to their scale, complexity, and resource demands. Instead, they required careful planning and organised labour of large groups. The building process, from planning to execution, requires deep knowledge of the landscape, the properties of materials, building skills, mobilisation of the workforce, and coordination of labour. We estimated that the building process, from stone extraction and minimal shaping, transporting stones, and finally stacking walls and structures, required around 110,000 person-hours for the largest structure K01, around 54,000 and 50,000 for K02 and K04, and around 19,000 person-hours for the smallest

structure K03. Those are enormous numbers that require a large workforce and coordination of work. Thus, for example, if a structure such as K01 is to be built during one season (4 months) with a 9-hour workday, it requires around 100 people to build, not including supervision and coordination.

Discussion and conclusions

Based on their construction and analogies with the arid parts of the Old World, we argue that these were uniquely hunting structures, megatraps for hunting wild game¹³. Their shape, construction, and placement are directly comparable to similar structures in North Africa, the Near East, and the Caucasus.

The shape of structures with converging driving lines placed in strategic positions in a landscape is designed to lead and guide animals towards the terminal enclosure. The construction of concealed cells below the crags and cliffs clearly indicates a purpose focused on hunting rather than the corralling of domesticated animals. This is also the strongest argument that structures function as large-scale hunting structures specifically engineered to capture herds of wild animals.

This conclusion is also supported by GIS analyses of structures. Their location, size, and orientation were carefully chosen to maximise their effectiveness in complex topographies by channelling animals towards well-concealed traps. They are positioned on the natural movement corridors in the landscape, which indicates that they were designed to migrate herds of animals.

Although the dating of buildings and use of these structures remains inconclusive, radiocarbon dating suggests they were used before the Bronze Age. An additional argument for age older than the Bronze Age is that they are not comparable with structures built for herding animals, which can be associated with the horizon of Bronze Age clearance and the

formation of a pastoral landscape centred around hillforts. Moreover, since they were constructed to hunt wild game, we assume they predate the adoption of domestic animals in the Karst at around 7500 BP^{23,26}. Therefore, they might be of Mesolithic age or older. The Mesolithic age is further supported by the distribution of Mesolithic sites on the Karst, where we can observe three concentrations of sites near main communication corridors, where traps were erected.

There are other unanswered questions. First, what kind of animals were hunted? In the arid Near East, such structures are built mainly for hunting herd animals such as gazelles. Archaeological evidence shows the most commonly hunted animal in the Karst during the Mesolithic was deer^{21,29-31}. For example, in the Mesolithic layers of Grotta dell'Edera (Stenašča), located in the vicinity of the K03 structure, red deer comprise almost 90 % of the faunal assemblage. In this period, Grotta dell'Edera was visited seasonally, and most of the deer were hunted in spring, while mortality profiles indicate the presence of a spectrum of age classes, including both young and adult individuals. In the Neolithic layers, deer is almost completely replaced by domestic animals such as sheep and goats and comprises less than 10% of the faunal assemblage³². In the Bronze Age, hunted animals generally represented less than 10 % of the faunal assemblage.

What was the environment in which they were built? In the Near East, such structures are typically found in arid, open landscapes, including deserts and steppes. An open environment is essential for the visibility of driving lines, allowing them to guide herds across the terrain effectively. In contrast, low guiding walls would be obscured by vegetation in densely forested landscapes, making them far less functional. However, the last time Karst was open was probably in the Late Glacial when Karst was an inhospitable plateau rising above the North Adriatic plain, with the Adriatic Sea several 10 km to the south. However, we do not have any evidence of human presence at the time³³. Such environmental conditions

must have persisted also in the first stages of the Holocene. Therefore, if the structures are of the Mesolithic age, we must assume at least some limited vegetation management to enhance the visibility of driving lines and facilitate more effective hunting.

In any case, they represent the largest known prehistoric structures in the region and Europe. Significant energy and organisation were required to build and operate them. This opens up the last questions. Megastructures built to hunt mobile herds of wild game require careful planning, a large workforce, communal effort, work organisation, well-thought-out strategies, adapted hunting techniques, deep knowledge of landscape, regional ecology, and animal behaviour, and demand for large quantities of hunted animals. Such large structures also have an impact on the local ecosystems.

The discovery of prehistoric megastructures designed for hunting wild game, comparable to those found in North Africa, the Near East, and the Caucasus, raises new questions about the complexity of hunter-gatherer communities in the North Adriatic hinterland. It opens the possibility that large groups of hunters migrated northward in response to rising sea levels, settling in the upland regions of the North Adriatic, where they may have introduced or independently developed new hunting technologies.

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Methods

Slovenian nationwide aerial laser scanning data acquired in 2014 and 2015 was used for this study. The laser scanning covered the entire territory of Slovenia, with a 250 m overlap along the Italian border. The dataset had a horizontal accuracy of 30 cm and a vertical accuracy of 15 cm, with a point density of 5 pulses/m² for the study area.

The point cloud was reclassified using LAStools *lasground* algorithm with the *-archaeology* parameter. A digital elevation model (DEM) with a resolution of 0.5 m was then generated from classified ground points using the *blast2dem* algorithm ¹.

For the Italian portion of the study area, which was not covered by Slovenian laser scanning data, Friuli Venezia Giulia (FVG) Region LiDAR-derived DEMs with a resolution of 1 m were used.

To enhance terrain interpretation, the Relief Visualization Toolbox (RVT) was used to generate key visualizations, including hillshade, sky-view factor, and local relief models ². Relevant features were then manually digitized in QGIS for further analysis.

Standing stone structures were recorded using a drone and handheld camera photogrammetry, which was complemented by a portable laser scanner embedded in a mobile phone for enhanced spatial accuracy and detail.

A 5 × 1 m test trench was excavated perpendicular to the cell in the K01 structure, positioned parallel to the crag. The trench covered the western wall and the interior of the pit. Drone and handheld photogrammetry were used to document plans, sections, and the volume of removed stones. Five stratigraphic units (SU) were identified:

- SU01: Comprised of large limestone boulders and humus, interpreted as the collapsed pit wall.
- SU02: A layer of dark reddish-brown silty clay, interpreted as the buried ground surface within the pit.
- SU03: A deposit of reddish-brown silty clay (*terra rossa*).
- SU04: A dry-stone wall, irregularly stacked with two faces, constructed using large, irregular limestone boulders, with the interior packed with smaller stones and rubble.
- SU05: Limestone bedrock, exposed in places, with deep grikes filled by SU04.

In the SU0 we recovered three charcoal fragments and a lithic fragment. No other artefacts were found. Three samples of oak (*Quercus*) charcoal, each less than 1 cm in size, were excavated from layer SU03, approximately 0.8 m below the surface. The samples were sent to the Poznań Radiocarbon Laboratory for AMS dating after identification. The resulting conventional radiocarbon dates were 2515 ± 30 BP (Poz-1844819), 1775 ± 30 BP (Poz-184385) and 3185 ± 30 BP (Poz-184387). Calibration to calendar years was performed using the IntCal20 calibration curve within the OxCal program, yielding the following calibrated date ranges: 786–543 BC, 216–363 AD and 1506–1411 BC (2-sigma ranges).

A 0.5 m-resolution ALS-derived DEM was resampled to 1 m resolution for visibility analysis. The analyses were conducted using the Visibility Analysis plugin in QGIS³. Pit visibility: Viewsheds were calculated from digitized pit locations. Guiding wall visibility: Digitized walls were sampled at 1 m intervals,

and cumulative visibility was calculated for each point. Total viewshed (visual index of the landscape): Visibility was computed for every point in the landscape and summed to create an overall visual exposure model.

All analyses were performed with a maximum radius of 5 km and an observer height of 1.6 m.

Architectural energetics were estimated for each structure based on material volume and labour costs, expressed in person-hours for stone extraction, shaping, transport, and construction.

The volume of the driving walls was estimated from 3D scans of multiple sections, indicating approximately 1 m³ of stone used per meter of wall. The total volume was calculated by multiplying this estimate by the wall length, as measured from digitized plans.

Pit wall volume calculations were based on excavations of the K01 apex pit. We assumed an original height of 2 m. The bottom width of 2.5 m was estimated based on excavation data, while the top width of 1.7 was reconstructed. We estimated an 80 % packing density with large stones. This gives the volume of 4.2 m³ of stones per metre of the pit wall.

Labour estimates were derived from a table of estimates collected by Abrams and McCurdy⁴. The building material consisted primarily of locally available limestone, which showed no significant shaping or dressing. Therefore, the extraction rate was estimated at 0.5 m³/person-hour. The stacking and building rate was estimated at 0.03 m³/person-hour.

These calculations were applied across all structures, using digitized plan measurements to estimate the total construction effort.

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